

Verification of NNs in the IMOCO4.E Project: Preliminary Results

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Abstract—In recent years, there has been growing interest in machine learning and neural networks within research and industrial communities. While neural networks have shown impressive capabilities across various domains, their practical applications are still limited in safety-critical contexts due to a lack of formal guarantees regarding their reliability and behavior. This paper explores the latest advancements in Satisfiability Modulo Theory (SMT) technologies for verifying neural networks with piece-wise linear and transcendent activation functions. Through experimental analysis, we evaluate these technologies using neural networks trained on a real-world predictive maintenance dataset. This research contributes to the ongoing efforts to enhance the safety and reliability of neural networks through formal verification, enabling their deployment in safety-critical domains.

Index Terms—Trustworthy AI, Neural Networks, Formal Methods

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last few years, there has been a notable surge of interest in Machine Learning (ML) and Neural Networks (NNs) from both the research and industrial communities. NNs have proven to possess remarkable capabilities across various domains within computer science [1], [2]. However, their applications encounter limitations in safety and security-sensitive scenarios due to the absence of formal guarantees regarding their reliability and behavior. Furthermore, NNs have been discovered to be susceptible to adversarial perturbations, where slight modifications to their inputs result in unforeseen and undesirable changes in their behavior [3]. Consequently, the research field of neural network verification, which focuses on providing formal guarantees for their behavior, has received significant attention [4]–[9].

This paper investigates the verification of neural networks in the predictive maintenance domain using recent advancements in Satisfiability Modulo Theory (SMT) technologies. To assess the impact of these advancements, we evaluate them on neural networks trained on a dataset for predictive maintenance derived from the ongoing “Intelligent Motion Control under Industry 4.E” (IMOCO4.E) project [10].

IMOCO4.E is a Key Digital Technologies Joint Undertaking (KTD JU) project started on September 2021. With the participation of 46 partners from 13 countries, its overarching objective is to push the boundaries of mechatronic systems

by enhancing their intelligence and adaptability. This goal will be realized through the integration and exploitation of novel sensory information, model-based approaches, AI, ML, and industrial IoT principles. By harnessing these advanced technologies, the project seeks to shape the transition of European manufacturing towards Industry 4.0, enabling the perception and management of sophisticated machinery and robotics. Specifically, it will deliver a reference architecture that will be tested and validated in several use cases and pilots in different industrial domains, such as applications for packaging, industrial robotics, healthcare, and semiconductors. In our work, we narrow down our attention to a particular use case related to the application of neural networks in the domain of elevator predictive maintenance. Elevators, being complex machines, require regular maintenance to ensure their safe and reliable operation. The control of elevator movement in tall buildings presents significant challenges due to non-linearity, uncertainty, and the dynamics of time-varying systems. By leveraging the power of neural networks for predictive maintenance, potential issues can be detected before they escalate into breakdowns or pose safety hazards. This proactive approach not only minimizes downtime but also enhances the overall performance of elevators.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. In Section II we introduce some basic concepts and definitions. In Section III we briefly present the related work and our motivations. In Section IV and V we introduce our experimental setup and present our preliminary results respectively. In Section VI we present some of our future research plans.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Neural Networks

A *sequential* neural networks is a machine-learning model consisting of interconnected computing units, commonly known as *neurons*. Such network present a structure composed by several sequential layers whose neurons are only connected to the neurons of the immediately previous and following layers. The first and the last layer of the network are called, respectively, *input* and *output* layers.

Computationally, the l -th layer of a sequential neural network can be defined as a function $f_l : \mathcal{I}_l \rightarrow \mathcal{O}_l$ where \mathcal{I}_l and \mathcal{O}_l represent respectively the input and output domain of

the function. Similarly, a generic sequential neural network can be defined as a function $\nu : \mathcal{I}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{O}_p$ where \mathcal{I}_1 and \mathcal{O}_p are, respectively the input (output) domain of both the first (last) layer of the network and of the network as a whole. In particular, the neural network function ν can be expressed as:

$$\nu(x) = f_p(f_{p-1}(\dots f_1(x)\dots)) \quad (1)$$

In this work, we are mainly focused on layers whose inputs and outputs consist of vectors of real numbers, therefore we will usually have $\mathcal{I}_l \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ and $\mathcal{O}_l \subseteq \mathbb{R}^m$.

The structure defined by the various layers of a neural network, their connections, and their hyper-parameters is commonly known as the network *architecture*. In this paper we focus on sequential neural networks presenting *linear layers* and *non-linear activation functions*. A linear layer applies to its input a simple affine transformation $y = Wx + b$, where $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $y \in \mathbb{R}^m$ are respectively the input and output vector and W and b are the learnable weight matrix and bias vector. The size m of the output is determined by the number of hidden neurons in the layer. An activation function layer, in general, applies a certain activation function to all the element of the vector provided as input. Here we consider ReLU, hyperbolic tangent and logistic activation functions.

B. Satisfiability Modulo Theory

Satisfiability Modulo Theories (SMT) focuses on the problem of deciding the satisfiability of a first-order formula with respect to some decidable theory \mathcal{T} , while an SMT instance is a formula in first-order logic where some function and predicate symbols have additional interpretations. If we consider a first-order formula ϕ in a decidable background theory \mathcal{T} , the satisfiability problem consists in deciding whether a model — *i.e.*, an assignment to the free variables in ϕ — that satisfies ϕ exists. It should be clear that SMT extends the Boolean satisfiability problem (SAT) by adding background theories such as the theories of real numbers, integers, and data structures.

The SMT-LIB language is a standardized language used for describing logical formulas in the context of Satisfiability Modulo Theories. It is an open and extensible language designed to support a variety of theories and solvers. The language consists of a set of syntactic and semantic rules for specifying logical formulas in various theories.

For a comprehensive background on SMT, we refer to [11].

C. Verification

As mentioned in Section I, the aim of formal verification is to provide formal guarantees about the compliance of a neural network with some specific property of interest. In particular, we focus on input-output specifications: that is, properties defining specific *preconditions* on the inputs of the neural network and corresponding *postconditions* that its outputs should respect.

Definition 1: Given a neural network $\nu : \mathcal{I} \rightarrow \mathcal{O}$, a generic input $x \in \mathcal{I}$ and the corresponding output $y \in \mathcal{O}$, we can define an input-output property Φ as a couple

$\Phi = \langle \phi_I(x), \phi_O(y) \rangle$ where the precondition $\phi_I(x)$ and the postcondition $\phi_O(y)$ are first order logic (FOL) formulas with x and y occurring as free variables.

Given this definition, the problem of proving that a network $\nu : \mathcal{I} \rightarrow \mathcal{O}$ is compliant with a property $\Phi = \langle \phi_I(x), \phi_O(y) \rangle$ consist in proving the validity of the following formula:

$$\forall x. \forall y. (\phi_I(x) \wedge y = \nu(x)) \implies \phi_O(y). \quad (2)$$

If the formula is valid, then the property is verified for all possible x , otherwise it exists at least a *counter-example* \hat{x} for which the formula is violated.

It should be clear that verifying a set of properties \mathcal{P} consists of verifying separately each property $\Phi \in \mathcal{P}$: if Equation 2 is valid for every property Φ , then ν is compliant with the set of property \mathcal{P} , otherwise some property $\Phi \in \mathcal{P}$ will admit a counter-example and, as consequence, ν will not be compliant with \mathcal{P} .

III. RELATED WORKS

The idea of utilizing SMT solvers for neural network verification is not entirely novel, as evidenced by the first paper [12] from 2010, where the tool NEVER employed the HYSAT solver [13] and abstract interpretation to verify a simple multi-layer perceptron, which is the precursor to modern NNs. In a subsequent work [14] in 2012, the authors expanded their methodology and compared the performance of various SMT solvers on a set of benchmarks involving different perceptron architectures and properties of interest. Another approach proposed in [15] leveraged both a linear programming solver and an SMT solver, employing a specific network encoding and property representation to enable verification of fully-connected NNs with ReLU activation functions. Furthermore, in [16], a novel \mathcal{T} -solver optimized for handling ReLU activation functions was introduced and tested on the ACAS XU benchmark, which consists of networks and properties from the aviation domain.

In contrast, our work aligns more closely with the methodology employed in [14]. Specifically, our focus is to assess the behavior of current state-of-the-art SMT solvers when confronted with the task of verifying a neural network with non-linear activation functions, without modifying existing methodologies or utilizing optimized network encodings. The advancements in SMT solvers over the past decade justify the need for the more recent experimental evaluation presented in this work.

For a comprehensive overview of the current state of the art regarding neural network verification, we recommend referring to [6].

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Property Definition

For our experimental evaluation, we focus on verifying the network's resilience against local perturbations in its input. These perturbations entail slight variations applied to the input vector, which can result in disproportionate changes in the network's output. This property aligns with the concept of

robustness against *adversarial perturbations* [3], a widely recognized reliability concern in classification networks.

The formal definition of our *safety* property of interest for a given input vector \hat{x} with corresponding output \hat{y} is:

$$\forall x. \forall y. (\|x - \hat{x}\|_\infty \leq \varepsilon \wedge y = \nu(x)) \Rightarrow \|y - \hat{y}\|_\infty < \delta \quad (3)$$

where ε and δ are, respectively the maximum magnitude of the perturbation and the maximum acceptable magnitude of the variance on the corresponding output. $\|x(y) - \hat{x}(\hat{y})\|_\infty$ is the Chebyshev norm of the difference between the original feature vector (output) and the perturbed one.

Due to the universal quantification, proving that Equation 3 holds is unfeasible for most solvers. As consequence, we define the following *unsafety* property:

$$\exists x. \exists y. (\|x - \hat{x}\|_\infty \leq \varepsilon \wedge y = \nu(x)) \Rightarrow \|y - \hat{y}\|_\infty \geq \delta \quad (4)$$

It should be clear that, if the unsafety property of Equation 4 is valid then its model is a counter-example for the safety property of Equation 3, which is thus violated.

In our experimental evaluation we considered three different values of ε (10^{-1} , 10^{-2} , 10^{-3} respectively) and two different values of δ (1 and 10^{-1} respectively) for each network architecture.

B. Dataset and Networks

The dataset utilized to train the relevant networks pertains to the same application domain as the IMOCO4.E elevator use case mentioned in Section I. Moreover, the network architectures considered bear similarity to those under evaluation within the aforementioned case studies. Specifically, we employ the Electric Motor Temperature dataset, comprising 185 hours of sensor recordings from a permanent magnet synchronous motor (PMSM) deployed on a test bench. The recordings are sampled at a rate of 2 Hz, and the dataset encompasses multiple measurement sessions ranging from one to six hours. The dataset presents 12 distinct features, corresponding to measurements acquired from various sensors. In our case study, the objective is to predict the stator tooth and yoke temperature, as well as the motor torque, based on the remaining features. For further insights into the interpretation of each feature, we refer to [17], [18] and the dataset’s Kaggle page¹. All the data points are normalized within the range of 0 to 1 or -1 to 1, depending on the activation function employed in the respective network.

Considering the chosen case study, our focus is on fully-connected neural networks that employ non-linear activation functions, which have proven successful in regression tasks across various domains. Our network architectures consist of one or more blocks, each comprising a fully connected layer followed by an activation function layer, and finally a fully connected output layer without an activation function. We refer to the layers within these blocks as intermediate layers. All fully-connected layers within the architectures lack biases, and the output layer size is consistently set to three, corresponding

to the number of quantities we aim to predict. We evaluated three architectures with a single block, featuring 16, 32, and 64 neurons, respectively. Additionally, two architectures with two blocks were considered, consisting of 8 and 16 neurons for the first block, and 16 and 34 neurons for the second block. As indicated in Subsection II-A, the activation functions considered were ReLU, hyperbolic tangent, and the logistic function.

Following training, all networks demonstrated satisfactory performance in the given task, with a test loss computed using the Mean Square Error (MSE) function below 10^{-3} .

We leveraged PYNEVER [4], which employs PYTORCH as its training backend, to train the networks. We allocated 20% of the dataset as a test set and of the remaining data, 30% was used as a validation set. Our loss function was the MSE, and we trained each network for 5 epochs. The batch sizes were 1024, 512, and 1024 for the training, validation, and test sets, respectively. We utilized the Adam optimizer with its default parameters and evaluated our models based on the MSE metric. For additional information on the learning parameters, the PYTORCH documentation may be consulted.

C. Solvers

The selection of SMT solvers for our experimental evaluation was guided by the results of SMT-COMP 2022. We specifically favored solvers that supported the use of transcendental functions as activation functions in our networks, namely the logistic and hyperbolic tangent functions. Our final choices for solvers were CVC5 [19], MATHSAT [20], Z3 [21], and YICES2 [22]. The first two solvers support both piece-wise linear and transcendental functions, while the latter two only support piece-wise linear functions.

V. RESULTS

The experiments were conducted on a Dell PowerEdge T640 workstation equipped with 256 GB of RAM and a 3.60 GHz (16 Cores) Intel Xeon Gold CPU. The operating system used was Ubuntu 22.04.1 LTS. The verification queries were consistently launched with the default parameters of the solver.

The results of our experimental evaluation are presented in Fig. 1. It is important to note that a total of 90 queries were considered, with 30 queries for each type of activation function, obtained by combining different architectures with specific ε and δ values. However, only MATHSAT consistently managed to solve some queries with transcendental activation functions before the 1-hour timeout. Consequently, the number of solved queries reported is lower than the total number considered. Regarding the performance of the solvers, MATHSAT achieved the highest number of successfully solved benchmarks, followed by CVC5, Z3, and YICES2. Analyzing Fig. 1, it is evident that while MATHSAT and CVC5 solved the most queries, Z3 and YICES2 often required less time to obtain results for the queries they were able to solve within the timeout. However, considering that the verification of neural networks typically occurs during the design and

¹<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/wkingsn/electric-motor-temperature>

Fig. 1. Graphical representation of the results of our experimental evaluation. The x-axis represents the number of queries solved before reaching the timeout of 1 hour, while the y-axis represents the corresponding time needed (on a logarithmic scale).

training stages of these models, we believe that the number of solved queries is the most significant metric. Overall, it appears that MATHSAT is well-suited for the task of neural network verification, surpassing expectations based on its performance in the SMT-COMP 2022 competition. Similarly, CVC5 performed favorably, which aligns with its previous success as the winner of the QF_NRA division in the Single Query Track of SMT-COMP 2022.

VI. FUTURE WORKS

In our future work, we plan to expand our experimental evaluation by incorporating additional case studies from the IMOCO4.E project. This will allow us to explore a wider range of network architectures and their applicability to different domains. Furthermore, we are actively researching ways to enhance existing verification methodologies based on abstract interpretation. Our aim is to extend these techniques to accommodate recurrent neural networks and other learning models that have been effectively applied in predictive maintenance tasks.

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